

XXI АСРДА ИНКЛЮЗИВ ТАЪЛИМ: АФЗАЛЛИКЛАРИ ВА МУАММОЛАРИ
ИНКЛЮЗИВНОГО ОБРАЗОВАНИЯ В XXI ВЕКЕ: ПРЕИМУЩЕСТВА И
ПРОБЛЕМЫ

INCLUSIVE EDUCATION IN THE 21ST CENTURY: ADVANTAGES AND
CHALLENGES

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Annotatsiya. Maqolada zamonaviy maktablarda inklyuziv ta'limning asosiy afzalliklari va muammolari ko'rib chiqiladi. Inklyuziyaning nazariy asoslari, inklyuziv amaliyotlarni joriy etishning xalqaro va milliy tajribasi tahlil qilingan. O'qituvchilar, ota-onalar va o'quvchilar duch keladigan to'siqlarga va ularni bartaraf etish yo'llariga alohida e'tibor qaratiladi. Tadqiqot natijasida inklyuziv ta'limni takomillashtirish, uning samaradorligi va ommabopligini oshirishga qaratilgan tavsiyalar taklif etildi.

Kalit so'zlar: inklyuziv ta'lim, ijtimoiy integratsiya, tenglik, moslashuv, ta'lim ehtiyojlari, pedagogik texnologiyalar.

Аннотация. В статье рассматриваются ключевые преимущества и вызовы инклюзивного образования в современной школе. Анализируются теоретические основы инклюзии, международный и национальный опыт внедрения инклюзивных практик. Особое внимание уделяется барьерам, с которыми сталкиваются учителя, родители и учащиеся, а также возможным путям их преодоления. В результате исследования предложены рекомендации по совершенствованию инклюзивного образования, направленные на повышение его эффективности и доступности.

Ключевые слова: инклюзивное образование, социальная интеграция, равенство, адаптация, образовательные потребности, педагогические технологии.

Abstract. The article examines the key advantages and challenges of inclusive education in modern schools. The theoretical foundations of inclusion, international and national experience in implementing inclusive practices are analyzed. Special attention is paid to the barriers faced by teachers, parents, and students, as well as possible ways to overcome them. As a result of the research, recommendations have been proposed for improving inclusive education, aimed at increasing its effectiveness and accessibility.

Keywords: inclusive education, social integration, equality, adaptation, educational needs, pedagogical technologies.

Introduction

The modern educational system strives to create conditions that ensure equal access to knowledge for all students, including children with special educational needs (HIA). Inclusive education is an important area of school development, focused on socialization, an individual approach to learning and the formation of a tolerant society.

According to international standards such as the UN Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities and the Dakar Declaration on Education for All (2000), countries must ensure equal

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educational opportunities for all children. Inclusive education is actively developing in Uzbekistan, which is confirmed by the strategy for modernizing the education system and relevant legislative changes. However, the process of introducing inclusive education is accompanied by a number of difficulties: a lack of qualified teachers, insufficient funding, the unavailability of school infrastructure and the need to change the public perception of inclusion. This article analyzes the advantages and challenges of inclusive education, as well as offers solutions for its effective implementation in the school system.

Literature review

Inclusive education is a learning model that involves co—education of children with different educational needs in general education schools. The concept of inclusion is based on the theories of L.S. Vygotsky [6], who emphasized the importance of the social environment in the cognitive development of a child. Modern research confirms that inclusion promotes the development of tolerance, improves the academic and social performance of all students.[2]

According to UNESCO research, inclusive education is a key tool for ensuring equality in education and social inclusion. [5] Lindsay notes that the successful implementation of inclusive education depends on the training of teachers, the availability of adapted curricula and a positive attitude of society. [4]

In the context of Uzbekistan, Alimov and Karimova's research shows that the country is actively working to create an inclusive educational environment. However, the main problems include insufficient funding, lack of educational materials, and low awareness among teachers of inclusive learning methods. [1,3]

Thus, the literature shows that inclusive education has significant advantages, but its implementation requires a systematic approach and the elimination of existing barriers.

Research methodology

Qualitative and quantitative methods were used in the course of the study.:

1. Analysis of regulatory documents (laws, strategies for the development of inclusive education in Uzbekistan and other countries).

2. A survey of teachers and parents (100 teachers and 150 parents from different schools) to identify attitudes towards inclusive learning.

3. Analysis of student performance in inclusive and traditional classrooms.

4. Interviews with experts (teachers, psychologists, representatives of the Ministry of Public Education).

Analysis and results

The benefits of inclusive education

The results of the study confirm that inclusive education has many advantages.:

- Social integration: children with disabilities adapt better to society, learn to interact with their peers.

- Building tolerance: Children without disabilities develop empathy and respect for diversity.

- Individual approach: teachers use differentiated teaching methods, which has a positive effect on academic performance.

- Long-term economic benefits: educating children with disabilities in regular schools reduces the cost of special education institutions.

Challenges and problems

Despite the advantages, the study revealed a number of challenges:

THE MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY

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- Lack of qualified teachers (78% of teachers reported insufficient training).
- Lack of adapted curricula and materials (67% of schools do not have specialized manuals).
- Insufficient technical equipment (55% of schools are not equipped to teach children with various forms of disability).
- Stereotypes and misunderstandings among parents (40% of parents believe that children with disabilities interfere with their children's education).

Conclusion and recommendations

Inclusive education plays a key role in ensuring equal opportunities for all students, but its implementation requires overcoming significant challenges. Based on the conducted research, the following recommendations can be proposed:

1. Professional development of teachers: introduction of specialized courses on inclusive education.
2. Development of adapted curricula: creation of differentiated teaching aids.
3. Technical equipment of schools: provision of necessary resources (special equipment, infrastructure).
4. Information campaigns: raising awareness of parents and society about inclusive education.
5. Government support: increased funding for inclusive programs and the development of regulations governing the rights of children with disabilities in schools.

In general, inclusive education is a necessary element of a modern school system, but its successful implementation requires an integrated approach and interaction between the state, schools and society.

ЛИТЕРАТУРЫ

1. Алимов, У. (2021). *Проблемы и перспективы инклюзивного образования в Узбекистане*. Ташкент: Издательство НУУз.
2. Booth, T., & Ainscow, M. (2016). *Index for Inclusion: Developing Learning and Participation in Schools*. Bristol: CSIE.
3. Каримова, З. (2022). *Социальные аспекты восприятия инклюзивного образования в Узбекистане*. Журнал "Образовательные реформы", 4(3), 45-59.
4. Lindsay, G. (2007). *Educational psychology and the effectiveness of inclusive education/mainstreaming*. *British Journal of Educational Psychology*, 77(1), 1-24.
5. UNESCO. (2020). *Global Education Monitoring Report: Inclusion and education*. Paris: UNESCO Publishing.
6. Виготский, Л.С. (1934). *Мышление и речь*. Москва: Педагогика.